

PREDICTING TRENDS IN STRUCTURAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF HYBRID POLYMER COMPOSITES USING MOLECULAR DYNAMICS.

K. Prasad^{1,*}, M. Nikzad¹, and I. Sbarski¹

1 Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology, Swinburne University of Technology, Melbourne, Australia

* Corresponding author- krishnamurthyprasad@swin.edu.au

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ABSTRACT

Using Molecular Dynamics (MD), molecules of LLDPE and pine flour were constructed. The material properties of the molecules, specifically microporosity and elastic moduli, were compared to experiment. A semi empirical modelling approach was used to fit the simulated data to the experimental composite moduli. The model of Carman and Reifsnider and that of Halpin and Tsai were found to be the most efficacious for this system and the benefits of the combined MD-semi empirical modelling for bottom up design is discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

For the polymer market at large, packaging and storage are the major areas of usage and thus, extensive research has been carried out on the prediction and modelling of the transport of several permeants through polymers and their composites. Amongst the polymers used are semicrystalline Polyethylene (PE), Polyethyleneterephthalate (PET), Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and Nylon. These materials are used in many different forms ranging from membranes to large-scale storage units. [1]. Recently, our research group compiled all the available literature into a review on the various aspects to be taken into account in order to design strong and viable polymeric storage units [2]. Amongst the systems analysed, polymer natural fibre composite systems are quite attractive from economic, sustainability and environmental friendliness standpoints [3-5]. However, it has to be noted the presence of the natural fibres in a polymer matrix creates porosity at the interfaces owing to the interfacial tension between the hydrophilic fibres and the relatively hydrophobic polymer and thus, optimization of natural fibre concentration is a very important aspect of designing such systems for packaging applications [5].

Molecular Dynamics (MD) provides a unique way of visualizing and analyzing material systems at extremely low time and length scales associated with molecular interactions and consequently predicting bulk phenomena. Influence of process variations, impurities and human errors can be eliminated and macroscopic properties can be predicted with high accuracy [6-7].

The effectiveness of MD in combination with semi empirical modelling for bottom up design was demonstrated previously by us when modelling oxygen diffusion in semi crystalline PE [8]. In this work, MD was used to simulate both semicrystalline PE and pine flour. As wood is a quite complex composite material and our pine flour simulation cell was built using the major phases in the pinewood viz., cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and water. By using various MD protocols, the constructed molecules were validated by comparing the simulated values of elastic moduli, microporosity and density with experimental values. By ensuring that the microporosity of the constructed systems were comparable to experimental values, the influence of macroporosity on the material properties could be isolated.

Finally, the simulated values were used to predict absolute and relative moduli values for our composites to rigorously validate our simulated molecules. We also check which of the various semi empirical models in literature were able to predict the real modulus values (obtained from Dynamic

Mechanical Analysis and nano indentation- more details are in Section 2.2) with the highest degree of accuracy and also suggest ways to improve such predictive ability to facilitate bottom up design.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

LLDPE with brand name Alkatuff LL710UV was provided by Price Plastics Pty. Ltd., Dandenong, Victoria. Untreated fine pine flour obtained from a *Pinus Radiata* source was purchased from Pollard's Sawdust Supplies Pty. Ltd., Plenty, Victoria. Samples were made by compression molding carried out at 190 °C at a pressure of 7600-10000 kPa.

2.2 Methods

MD simulations were carried out using the Materials and Process Simulation (MAPS) Platform: Version 4.0.1, France, (2018) developed by Scienomics Inc and run on the gstar High Performance Cluster (HPC) at Swinburne University of Technology. The development of the amorphous and crystalline versions of PE, building the respective simulation cells and using those simulations to model the diffusion of oxygen through LLDPE was shown in [8]. SciPCFF force field was used to simulate the PE specimens. Cellulose and hemicellulose monomers with *ab initio* charges assigned to the terminal chain atoms were constructed using the Sketching tool of the MAPS program and the systems were optimised using pcff as the forcefield. The monomer unit for the lignin molecule (Figure 2D) was adapted from Dabral et. al. [9]. The cellulose molecule had a degree of polymerization of 25 and two molecules were generated with an overall empirical formula of $C_{600}H_{1004}O_{500}$, the hemicellulose molecule has a DP of 13 and an overall empirical formula of $C_{507}H_{703}O_{327}$ and the lignin molecule had a DP of 5 and an empirical formula of $C_{430}H_{462}O_{145}$. The cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin molecules were combined to form a single simulation box of a wood molecule with the weight ratios were 40:30:30 by weight to approximate the proportions of the cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin molecules in softwood [10]. The overall empirical formula of this system was $C_{600}H_{1004}O_{500}$ and to this system molecules of water were introduced which constituted 8% by weight of the overall system which was the equilibrium amount of moisture in our pine flour measured on a TA Thermogravimetric Analyzer. This system was used to approximate the pine flour dispersed in the LLDPE matrix. Examples of the PE and wood simulation boxes (supercell) are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively.

The simulated systems were also analysed using the Trajectory Analysis module of the MAPS program. Using this module, the pore size distribution and free volume were estimated. Through this module a probe of zero diameter can be introduced into the simulation box post construction and equilibration. This is used to estimate parameters such as free volume, pore size distribution and the diameters of the largest included sphere in the system. A bin width of 0.1 Å was used to obtain the distribution.

Dynamic mechanical analysis of the molded samples were done in tensile mode under a temperature ramp from 30 °C to 100 °C. The trend in modulus values obtained from the experiments at 30 °C, 60 °C and 90 °C were compared with the moduli from MD analysis for the LLDPE system. Modulus values for the simulated pine flour were compared with experimental modulus obtained from nano-indentation analysis at 30 °C to establish the methodology which is as follows: The methodology for measuring the elastic modulus of a simulated molecule is as follows:

1. The system obtained after NPT dynamics (Step 3) is enlarged/strained continuously in one direction and the instantaneous pressure in that direction is recorded while the other two directions are kept at the same initial (in our case, atmospheric) pressure.
2. This enlargement is done stepwise till the required maximum strain is reached. We carried out the simulation till about 10% of strain but for both the simulated PE and wood, the reported modulus values are those obtained at 1% of strain.
3. Total run time of simulation is 1 ns. 15 MD runs each were carried out at 30 °C (303 K) for the semicrystalline PE and the simulated pine flour For the semicrystalline PE specifically, 15 MD runs were also carried out at a temperature ramp from 30°C to 60°C and also 30°C to 90°C. The specific modulus values obtained were then compared to the simulated modulus

value at 30°C to estimate the relative drop in modulus. This relative drop at 60°C and 90°C were then compared with the experimental drop using data from Dynamic Mechanical Analysis in tensile mode.

Finally, several semi empirical models designed for polymer composite systems were used in conjunction with the simulated values to see how accurately experimental trends in elastic moduli could be predicted and we also suggest ways to further improve such predictive ability to facilitate bottom up design.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Equilibrated simulation boxes of the amorphous and crystalline Polyethylenes are shown in Figure 1A and 1B respectively and a supercell of the wood simulation (to indicate some underlying structures) is shown in Figure 2. The equilibration algorithm was as follows:

1. An initial energy minimization step.
2. nvt (isochoric) ensemble run for 2 ns.
3. npt (isobaric) ensemble for 5 ns.

The pictures shown in Figures 1 and 2 are after the 5 ns npt run. The physical properties of the LLDPE and pine flour specimens were then compared with the simulated values. The specific properties measured were density (via pycnometry) and pore size (via Positron Annihilation Lifetime Spectroscopy- PALS). These values are shown in Table 1. An average pore diameter of 5 Å for the simulated PE is seen as compared to the experimental pore diameter of 6.45 Å observed via PALS. In terms of density, the simulated PE molecules had a density ($0.80 \pm 0.05 \text{ g/cm}^3$) that was about 17% lower than the density of the actual raw material (0.96 g/cm^3 -Alkatuff LL710UV). However, the densities of the building blocks of the semicrystalline PE i.e. the simulated 100% amorphous ($0.83 \pm 0.03 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and 100% crystalline PE ($1.04 \pm 0.04 \text{ g/cm}^3$) had densities very close to experimental values (0.855 g/cm^3 [11] for amorphous PE and 1 g/cm^3 [12] for 100% crystalline PE). A lower density for the simulated PE can be attributed to the fact that, while the construction and equilibration of a semicrystalline system was done, a true semicrystalline polymer is characterized by the presence of an interfacial region between the amorphous and crystal regions. This interface represents a transitional region from the order of the crystal to the isotropy and randomness of the amorphous state [13]. This cannot occur abruptly and the continuity of the long polymer chains imposes severe constraints on the transition. In our system, the transition from amorphous to crystalline happens abruptly and thus, the several transitional regions in this interface are not represented. This could be the reason that density of the simulated molecule does not measure up to the density of real polyethylene. The average pore size observed for the simulated wood flour is 4.50 Å which is close to the experimental pore size of $4.83 \pm 0.06 \text{ Å}$. In addition, the density of the simulated pine is $1.33 \pm 0.03 \text{ g/cm}^3$ which is also close to the experimental density of $1.27 \pm 0.03 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for the pine flour. Both of these results indicate that the simulated molecule is quite similar to the real pine flour in terms of its microporosity.

Figure 1: Simulating semicrystalline LLDPE. Orange = Crystalline, Blue = Amorphous.

Figure 2: Pine flour simulation supercell with hemicellulose in green, cellulose in black, lignin in red and water in white.

Table 1: Simulated and experimental properties.

System	Property	Experiment	Simulated
LLDPE	Pore size (\AA)	6.45 ± 0.05	5.00 ± 0.10
	Density (g/cm^3)	0.94 ± 0.01	0.80 ± 0.05
	Modulus (GPa)	0.50 ± 0.05	0.69 ± 0.07
Pine flour	Pore size (\AA)	4.83 ± 0.06	4.50 ± 0.10
	Density (g/cm^3)	1.27 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.03
	Modulus (GPa)	3.65 ± 1.40	5.70 ± 1.63

Based on optical microscopy results, the aspect ratio ‘a’ of the pine flour particles was found to be 4.7 while Poisson’s ratio ‘ σ ’ of the matrix polymer LLDPE is 0.44 [14]. The relative change in elastic modulus of the PE-pine flour composite as a function of pine flour weight fraction are presented in Figure 3. The modulus value for the semicrystalline PE and the simulated pine flour were both higher than the experimental value. This overestimation can be attributed to the simulated molecules being idealised and also the inability to recreate processing created inconsistencies and voids in a MD environment.

Figure 3: Experimental and simulated trends in modulus of simulated LLDPE. E_i = modulus at 30°C, E = instantaneous modulus at that particular temperature.

The temperature ramp based simulation of elastic moduli of semicrystalline LLDPE is shown in Figure 3. The experimental modulus values were 538 MPa, 305 MPa and 135 MPa at 30°C, 60°C and 90°C corresponding to a relative drop of 43% and 75% at 60°C and 90°C compared to the value at 30°C. The simulated modulus values were 702 MPa, 461 MPa and 145 MPa at 30°C, 60°C and 90°C corresponding to a relative drop of 34% and 79% at 60°C and 90°C compared to the value at 30°C. Once again, the simulated values are higher than the experimental values but the relative drop in modulus is quite comparable to the experimental values. More improvement is needed to achieve higher accuracy and this can be obtained by incorporating co-monomers like octane in the simulation to more resemble the experimental LLDPE.

Several semi empirical models were then used to predict the composite moduli and are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Semi empirical models for predicting composite elastic moduli

Model	Expression	Reference
Rule of Mixtures	$E = (1 - \phi_D)E_C + \phi_D E_D$ <p>ϕ_D is the volume fraction of the dispersed phase while E, E_C and E_D are the moduli of the composite, continuous and dispersed phases respectively.</p>	[15]
Laminate	$E = [(1 - \phi_D)/E_C + \phi_D/E_D]^{-1}$	[15]
Carman Reifsnider	$E = E_\eta \phi_D + E_C (1 - \phi_D)$	[16]

	$E_{\eta} = \eta E_D$ $\eta = 1 - [\tanh(aK)/aK]$ $K = [-2E_C/(1+\sigma)/E_D/\ln(\phi_D)]^{1/2}$ <p>a and σ are the aspect ratio of the dispersed phase and Poisson's ratio of the continuous phase respectively.</p>	
Halpin Tsai	$E = E_C (1 + \beta\eta\phi_D)/(1 - \eta\phi_D)$ $\eta = [(E_D/E_C) - 1]/ [(E_D/E_C) + \beta]$ $\beta = 2(1-2\sigma)/(1+ \sigma)$ <p>σ is the Poisson's ratio of the continuous phase.</p>	[17]

Figure 4: Predicted trends in composite modulus and comparison with experimental values. E=modulus of composite, E=modulus of matrix LLDPE.

Amongst the models, the introduction of rigour into the model expression is done by incorporating characteristic parameters of the matrix polymer and the dispersed phase. The Carman-Reifsnider [17] and the Halpin-Tsai models [18] attempt this by using a and σ which are characteristic properties of the dispersed and continuous phases respectively. It can be seen that the use of these characteristic parameters helps in achieving accurate predictions of the trends in elastic moduli in the case of the Halpin-Tsai models. Further, the Halpin-Tsai approach can be customised for any and all composite systems. Also, more precise predictions can be obtained by improving the simulated systems by incorporating factors such as branching and co-monomers in the simulated molecules.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Using MD, both the constituent polymer and pine flour can be simulated on a molecular scale. By comparing and contrasting experimental data with MD data, the simulation can predict both structural properties such as density and atomistic pore sizes. When it comes to predicting trends in macroscopic properties such as elastic modulus, combination of MD with semi empirical models has potential. Best results are seen by using models that incorporate characteristic properties of the dispersed phase such as aspect ratio and that of the matrix polymer such as Poisson's ratio in the model expression. Based on that the Halpin Tsai and the Carman Reifsnider models seem best suited at this juncture. This combined approach can potentially be used for designing polymer networks with controllable properties from the bottom up.

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